

Poland

3rd wave survey – 2023

Age group

Data collection was carried out in **10 schools** and involved **729 students**.

Gender distribution

SES distribution

On average, adolescents reported **knowing very well** how to do 57% of the activities related to **technological and operational** support of digital media, but only 44% of the activities related to **information and navigation**.

Self-reported performance on skills increases with age for all groups of digital skills. In all categories, boys rate their skills higher than girls.

The average of correct answers to digital knowledge is 57%. Boys gave correct answers slightly more often than girls.

* Respondents answered a set of questions designed to measure their actual knowledge about how the internet and digital technologies work.

How digital literacy levels increase in adolescents who participated in three waves (261)?

In 2023, students achieved the highest level of skills in the dimension of **communication and interaction** (57%). The lowest level (44%) concerned **information and navigation skills**. The largest difference between the initial and final measurement (9%) is in the case of digital **content creation skills**.

Communication and interaction

Content creation and production

Information and navigation

Digital literacy* is a combination of digital skills and knowledge regarding how the internet and digital technologies work.

*The levels of digital literacy are a merger of self-reported high-level skills and the correct answer on the knowledge items. For technological and operational skills digital literacy could not be accounted for due to a lack of knowledge items.

Digital literacy increases with age. Boys present higher digital literacy levels (57%) in comparison to girls (47%), higher level of self-report digital skills (56% to 45%) and higher level of knowledge items (60% to 56%).